

Rebuttal Material

Q1: Details on how the partitioning is achieved. If the authors could expand on III C with more examples that would help shed light on what I think is a key part of the paper.

Answer: Thank you for your comments. A detailed example is shown in the following figure. The sorted transactions are first decomposed into multiple sub-transactions. These sub-transactions will be mapped to the corresponding threads according to the contract addresses they call. Each thread independently constructs a partition dependency graph based on the read-write relationship between sub-transactions, while maintaining the logical dependency between sub-transactions belonging to the same transaction.

Figure : Transaction decomposition and partition dependency graph construction